

MONITORING OF DELAMINATION ONSET IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES USING LAMB WAVE SIGNALS

D. Wang^{1,2}, Y. Lu¹, Y. Tang¹, L. Ye^{1*}

¹School of Aerospace, Mechanical and Mechatronic Engineering, The University of Sydney, NSW 2006, Australia

²Aeronautical Science and Technology Research Institute of COMAC, Commercial Aircraft Corporation of China, Ltd., Beijing 100083, People's Republic of China

*Corresponding author (Prof. Lin Ye, lin.ye@sydney.edu.au)

1 Introduction

Delamination is one of the major failure modes for composite laminates. To improve structural durability and damage tolerance, significant effort has been devoted to the characterization of delamination in composite laminates [1-5]. Double cantilever beam (DCB) and end notch flexure (ENF) tests have been widely conducted for characterizing Mode I (opening mode) and Mode II (sliding mode) delamination. Delamination onset is normally defined as the point when (i) deviation from linearity in the load-displacement curve (NL) occurs; (ii) delamination growth is visually observed on the edge (VIS) using bare eyes with or without assistance of a microscope; or (iii) the load has reached a maximum value (Max) in accordance with ASTM Standard D5528-01 [6] and ESIS protocol [7]. However, the NL, VIS and Max points are often determined in a somewhat subjective manner. In addition, it is widely acknowledged that visual inspection has not been very effective for characterizing Mode II delamination in ENF specimens.

In this study, a simple but reliable delamination monitoring method on the basis of Lamb wave propagation was proposed for characterizing Mode I and Mode II delamination onset in carbon fiber/epoxy (CF/EP) composite laminates. Piezoelectric elements were used for activating and capturing Lamb wave signals in the DCB and ENF specimens. Two delamination-sensitive wave parameters, i.e. propagation velocity and waveform similarity of the selected wave mode, were successively calculated in individual loading conditions during interlaminar fracture tests, where changes in these parameters were observed to be well correlated with delamination onset and growth. The Mode I and Mode II delamination onset were

therefore determined from the wave parameter-displacement curves and compared with those determined using the conventional methods.

2 Principle for Delamination Monitoring

Consider a composite laminate beam with edge delamination in the central plane, illustrated in Figure 1. Dual piezoelectric elements are surface-mounted at the top right and bottom left ends, acting as the actuator and sensor for the generation and acquisition of Lamb waves respectively, in a pitch-catch configuration. It is appreciated that the characteristics of Lamb waves propagating in a structure is significantly dependent on the host properties, in particular geometry parameters, e.g. thickness and curvature. For example, the propagation velocity of the fundamental asymmetrical Lamb wave mode (A_0) increases significantly with specimen thickness in the range of lower frequencies [8]. It can therefore be expected that the A_0 mode would propagate more quickly in the intact section (with whole laminate thickness) than in the delaminated section (with a half laminate thickness). The effective propagation velocity of the A_0 wave mode, v_e , measured by the sensor, is therefore relevant to the ratio of the delaminated propagation distance, d_d , to the intact propagation distance, d_i . The change in the effective propagation velocity of the A_0 wave mode, denoted by "VC", was calculated as the first delamination-sensitive wave parameter:

$$VC_i = \frac{v_{e,i} - v_{e,0}}{v_{e,0}} \quad (1)$$

where $v_{e,i}$ was the effective propagation velocity at the i -th loading condition and $v_{e,0}$ is the propagation velocity in the intact condition (without mechanical loading).

On the other hand, the degree of waveform similarity in the time domain between the activated signals, $\{y_{e,1}, y_{e,2}, \dots, y_{e,n}\}$, and the captured signals, $\{y_{r,1}, y_{r,2}, \dots, y_{r,n}\}$, is able to offer another essential clue for monitoring delamination. Accordingly, the correlation coefficient of the above two sets of signals (with the identical sampling period in the time domain), denoted by “CC”, was calculated as the second declamation-sensitive wave parameter:

$$CC_i = \frac{n \sum y_{e,i} y_{r,i} - \sum y_{e,i} \sum y_{r,i}}{\sqrt{[n \sum y_{e,i}^2 - (\sum y_{e,i})^2] [n \sum y_{r,i}^2 - (\sum y_{r,i})^2]}} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Principle of characterizing delamination onset in a composite laminate using Lamb wave signals

3 Experimental Details

A CF/EP composite laminate plate (250 mm × 250 mm × 3.60 mm), made of unidirectional carbon fabrics (ca. 60 vol%) and modified epoxy, was fabricated using the vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM). A non-adhesive thin film of polyimide with a thickness of 50 μm and a length of 100 mm was inserted in the central plane of the composite laminate at one end during the lay-up process to serve as an initiator for delamination. DCB and ENF specimens, with dimensions of 245 mm × 25 mm × 3.60 mm, were cut from the CF/EP composite laminate plate and used to conduct Mode I and Mode II interlaminar fracture tests, respectively. Rectangular piezoelectric elements (PI[®] PIC151 PZT ceramic, PQYY-0586), measuring 20 mm × 5 mm × 1 mm, with CuNi wrapped electrodes, were surface-mounted at the top right and bottom left ends of each specimen, shown in Figure 1. Aluminum loading blocks were bonded onto the DCB specimen to apply opening force for initiating and developing Mode I delamination while three-point bending was applied to accomplish Mode II interlaminar fracture test.

The fracture tests were conducted on a universal materials testing system (Instron[®] 5567) at a constant cross-head rate of 1 mm/min. The load and displacement curve was recorded to determine the NL, VIS, and Max points. Meanwhile, a VXI-based wave generation and acquisition system [9] was utilized and synchronized with the materials testing system. It consisted mainly of an arbitrary waveform generator (Agilent[®] E1441A), a piezo linear amplifier (PiezoSys[®] EPA-104), two 4-channel charge/voltage breakout boxes (Agilent[®] E3242A), and two analog-to-digital converters (ADC), providing 23-bits of raw resolution at the sample rate up to 20.48 MHz (Agilent[®] E1437A). The excitation wave signal (a 5-cycle sinusoidal toneburst enclosed in a Hanning window at a central frequency of 30 kHz) was activated with peak-to-peak voltage of 90 V and applied on the actuator. The response wave signals were captured by the sensor at a sampling rate of 5.12 MHz.

During Mode I or Mode II interlaminar fracture tests, the total time interval for activating, propagating and capturing Lamb wave signals using the wave generation and acquisition system was several orders of magnitude shorter than that for increasing the displacement using the universal materials testing system. Accordingly, each set of Lamb wave signals can be considered to be measured at a certain fixed condition with constant load and displacement, where VC and CC values were calculated and plotted versus displacement recorded by the materials testing system to construct the wave parameter-displacement curves.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Mode I delamination

The calculated VC and CC values to characterize Mode I delamination onset in a typical DCB interlaminar fracture specimen were plotted in Figure 2 in terms of cross-head displacement, with the load-displacement curve as a reference. A group of linear fitting curves was constructed using several branches of samples to facilitate the determination of VC and CC kink points. The intersections of these fitting curves indicated sudden changes for the calculated wave parameters. Theoretically, the wave propagation velocity for the DCB specimen remains constant before Mode I delamination onset due to the unchanged ratio of the delaminated to intact

sections, then it decreases immediately at the time of Mode I delamination onset, because the ratio of the delaminated to intact sections increases rapidly. The change in the degree of waveform similarity for the DCB specimen before and after Mode I delamination onset can be explained in the same way. However, two kink points, at which the almost constant VC and CC values began to decrease perceptibly, were observed in both the VC-displacement and CC-displacement curves, shown in Figure 2. The first observed VC and CC kink points were in fact correlated to the opening of the insert, which sometimes occurs in DCB specimens because the matrix resin may bond the insert film in some locations where the release agent is depleted.

Fig.2. Characterization of Mode I delamination onset in DCB specimen: (a) VC-; and (b) CC-displacement curves

By excluding the points corresponding to the opening of the insert, the second VC and CC kink

points could be determined as the time of Mode I delamination onset (Figure 2) in the DCB specimen. These kink points coincided almost exactly with the significant changes in the load-displacement curve, marked as NL, VIS, and Max points using the conventional methods. Moreover, the continued reduction in VC and CC values after the time of delamination onset may qualitatively represent Mode I delamination growth in the DCB specimen.

4.2 Mode II delamination

Figure 3 shows the wave parameter-displacement and load-displacement curves obtained for a typical ENF interlaminar fracture specimen to characterize Mode II delamination onset. Two kink points were also observed in the wave parameter-displacement curves. The first kink point was determined as the time of Mode II delamination onset in the ENF specimen and proved to be well synchronized with the NL, VIS, and Max points, which are also shown in Figure 3. On the other hand, the second kink point was not of interest in this study, because it in fact occurred when the delamination front approached the top loading position of the three-point bending fixture, after which greater force had to be applied to further develop Mode II delamination.

In comparison with the DCB counterpart, the kink points for the ENF specimen occurred at either the highest or lowest point in the wave parameter-displacement curves, facilitating the explicit identification of Mode II delamination onset. It is also interesting to observe that the wave propagation velocity for the ENF specimen increased before Mode II delamination onset, and then began to decrease after the time of Mode II delamination onset. A possible explanation for this unique phenomenon may be the semi-contact situation between the upper and lower beams of the ENF specimen before Mode II delamination onset, where bending moment slid the upper and lower beams and forced some parts into a semi-contact situation; this can be viewed as a reversal of the delamination growth (similar to “crack closure”), resulting in the increase in propagation velocity. In contrast, this situation was absent in the DCB specimen, where the tensile force opened the upper and lower beams and kept them in a complete non-contact situation.

Fig.3. Characterization of Mode II delamination onset in ENF specimen: (a) VC-; and (b) CC-displacement curves

5 Conclusions

A Lamb-wave-based delamination monitoring method was proposed and validated in Mode I and Mode II interlaminar fracture tests. Two delamination-sensitive wave parameters, i.e. propagation velocity (VC) and waveform similarity of the A_0 wave mode (CC), were calculated and correlated with delamination onset and growth in CF/EP composite laminates. The synchrony between the wave parameter-displacement and load-displacement curves was assessed in terms of the determined time of delamination onset.

It is concluded that Mode I and Mode II delamination onset can be characterized by interrogating the Lamb wave signals activated and

captured using the piezoelectric elements. In both the DCB and ENF tests, certain kink points could be observed in the wave parameter-displacement curves as the time of delamination onset. In comparison with conventional methods using indistinct NL, VIS, and Max points, the proposed method is particularly capable of characterizing Mode II delamination onset. This simple but reliable method on the basis of Lamb wave propagation is thus promising to monitor delamination onset and growth in composite laminates.

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